

Linguistic features of the Gainin dialect

Abdullina Gulfira Rifovna^{1*}, Alimbayeva Gulshayan Gabsalyamovna²

Ufa University of Science and Technology, Russian Federation

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*Corresponding Author

Abdullina Gulfira Rifovna

Ufa University of Science and Technology, Russian Federation.

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Abstract: *Objective.* The article is devoted to the analysis of the peculiarities of the language of the Gainin Bashkirs of the Bardymsky District of the Perm Territory on the basis of the field materials of the expedition organised in the summer of 2023. The novelty of the article lies in the fact that the peculiarities of the language of the Gainin Bashkirs of this region are studied in it from the point of view of the impact of socio-cultural and socio-political changes on them, as well as the identification of their specific features. *Materials and methods.* The linguistic material collected from the mouths of informants from over thirty localities of the above-mentioned region was subjected to comparative, perceptual, contextual and component analyses. *Results.* It was established that the language of the Gainin people is very original and differs from the dialects of the Bashkir and Tatar languages to a considerable extent by preserving ancient linguistic features, especially phonetic and morphological ones.

Keywords: dialect, dialect, dialecticism, phoneme, phonetic transition, isafet, verb.

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Introduction

The inevitable constant socio-economic and socio-political transformations taking place in the world have a direct impact on the entire spiritual culture of the people, including language. This is the reason for the urgent need to study the current state of the language of one of the most ancient Bashkir tribes, the Gaina, whose representatives live in the territory of the Bardymsky district of Perm Krai. It should be noted that there are a number of studies in the scientific literature devoted to the study of the dialectal peculiarities of the language of the Gaina Bashkirs. It should be noted here the works devoted to the study of the Northwestern dialect of the Bashkir language [Ishbulatov, 2000; Mirzhanova 2006; Shakur 2012; Baishhev 2016], lexicographic sources [Dictionary of Bashkir Dialects. Vol. 3: Western dialect, 1987; Dialectological dictionary of the Bashkir language, 2002], separate research articles [Abdullina, 2023]. Despite the available literature, the problem of learning the language of the Gainin Bashkirs from the point of view of the current state remains relevant.

Materials and methods

The theoretical and methodological basis of the research was the works on dialectology of the Bashkir language.

The data on language obtained from informants in over thirty settlements of the Bardymsky District of the Perm Territory with a compact settlement of Gaina Bashkirs served as the material for the study.

The main research method was comparative analysis, on the basis of which the collected linguistic material was considered in terms of comparison with the literary language of the Bashkir people. The methods of perceptual, contextual and component analyses were also used.

Results

Lexical peculiarities of the language of the Gaina Bashkirs

The Gaininsky dialect is characterised by the richness and originality of dialectisms. One of the peculiarities of this dialect is that the colloquial lexicon of the Gainins is closer to the Bashkir literary language than other dialects of the northwestern dialect, i.e. the main fund of the dialect is represented by lexical units of the Bashkir literary language: *mal* 'cattle', *kosh-kort* 'livestock', *yashelsa* 'vegetables', *syыр* 'cow', *sot* 'milk', *mai* 'butter', *kaimak* 'sour cream', *auyl* 'village', *urman* 'forest', *fat* 'earth', *igen* 'bread', *zhilak-zhimesh* 'berries, fruits', *haua* 'air', *shishma* 'spring', *ylga* 'river', etc., and others.

Among dialectisms in the vernacular there are notions from different spheres - names of: a) natural phenomena: *yayun* – *yamgyr* 'rain', *syulyk* – *ylga buyy* 'river bank'; b) objects of flora and fauna: *pechin* – *ylan* 'grass', *bakayafrak* – *yul yapragə* 'plantain', *pumalabash* – *bapembə* 'dandelion', *əməzho* – *кырау* *eləge* 'raspberry', *shartlama* – *ep eləge* 'strawberry', *shokmit* – *degənək* 'burdock', *kyzartky* – *talpan* 'tick', *koloki*, *kolki* – *kolon*

'colt', *koγash kort* – *koγash apay* 'ladybird'; c) household items, kitchen items: *tyrnauyshch* – *tyрма* 'rake', *biklameshch* – *kelә* 'bolt, bolt', *sozgho* – *choçko* 'trowel', *sәli* – *sәngeldәk* 'cradle', *eshmәk* – *tushәk* 'mattress', *tyniy* – *күгәкә буума* 'short valenki', *ilasә* – *beyәlәy* 'mittens', *tasqәk* – *lapaç*, *utynlyk* 'woodpile', *sortey* – *taçtamal* 'towel', *shchurnay* – *sәinyk* 'teapot', *shokor* – *sonayәk* 'cup', *shokortabәk* – *sonayәk açty* 'saucer', *tashaldyr* – *kәsә* 'bowl'; d) names of dishes: *bykmә* – *бөккәкән* 'pie', *әpek* – *әремсек* 'curd', *yз әpek* – *ыуыз әремсеге* 'curd made of colostrum'; e) kinship terms: *baldyz* 'sister-in-law' – *kәinesh* 'brother-in-law', *ylan* – *bala* 'child, child'.

In the lexicon there are also borrowings from the Russian language, practically adapted to the phonetics of the Bashkir language: *akhuta* – *telәk, dәrt* (Russian: hunting), *әngel* – *fәreshәtә* (Russian: angel), *biderә* – *kynәk, sylәk* (Russian: bucket), *botta* – *imesh* (Russian: as if), *bottoby* – *imeshter* (Russian: as if). bucket), *botta* – *imesh* (as if), *bottoby* – *imeshter* (as if), *gәrәchykә* – *kara* *boday* (buckwheat), *yzba* – *hut*, *darym* – *bush*, *bushlay* (*darom*), *dasuk* – *bush vakyt* (leisure), *kylәsә* – *tәgәrmәs* (wheel) and others.

The lexical and semantic features of the dialect are also reflected in stable phrases, phraseological phrases, proverbs and sayings: *күз кәйтмә* (досл. 'возвращение глаза') – *насар күрә башлау* 'ухудшение зрения', *бушкәйрәк* (досл. 'five tails') – *elbәzәk, eçel akyly* 'frivolous', *boz totou* (literally 'to hold ice') – *тиңуи, кәтүи, чуиңуи* 'to freeze, harden, cool', *astan әtkән* (literally 'scorching from below'). 'scorching from below') – *açtyrtyn keshe* 'a secretive person', *yakty kyз* (lit. 'bright eye') – *yakty vakyt* 'bright time of day', etc.

Phonetic peculiarities of the language of the Gaina Bashkirs

The following phenomena are characteristic of the phonetics of the Gaina colloquialism:

1) narrowing of the wide vowels *a, ә* in the position of the stressed closed syllable, which is especially observed in the diphthongic combinations *ay / әy* at the end of words, in particular, in pronoun-adjectives, pronoun-adverbs, also in the personal forms of present verbs: *Inde зurlar tpe әytsәk tә yary* (lit. *yaray*) (Nadyrov Rais Zaripovich, v. Stary Ashap). 'One can say that they are already grown up'. *Shundyj* (lit. *shundaj*) *ujynlar ujnanyk* (Baltacheva Khanifa Khanifovna, v. Bardabashka). 'These are the kind of games they used to play. *Kartupny utybyz* (lit. *utaybyz*), *alamasyin utybyz* (lit. *utaybyz*) *inde* (Yusupov Ilgizar Fasihovich, v. Verkh-Shlyk). 'Potatoes were weeded, weeds were weeded'. *Iptәsh kyzlarым belән shulyy uynybyzyy* (lit. *uinay inek*) (Akbasheva Rashida Shamsemunirovna, v. Mostovaya). 'With girlfriends they used to play like this';

2) transition of the diphthong *өy* to *өy // y*: *Menә hәzer min sulәshsәm* (lit. *hәylәshshәm*), *sez any anң lamatassyz da, bәlki* (Akbasheva Rashida Shamsemunirovna, v. Mostovaya). 'If I speak now, you probably won't understand me'. *Maktaptә ukyaanda bezdә yrәtәlәreye* (lit. *әjrәtәlәр ine*) *bayanda uynarga* (Mustaeva Ramilya Raifovna, v. Sarashi). 'While studying at school they taught us to play the bayan'. *Yashlәр dә dingә tartylalar. Ul da sәyenesh* (lit. *hәyөнәs*) (Mansurova Gulsira Minnegalimovna, v. Syuzyan). 'And young people are getting involved in religion. This is also pleasing. *Әле бүгенә хәтлә безнең өйләрәдә* (lit. *әjzәrзә*) *gas belә kyзdyryla* (Mustaeva Ramilya Raifovna, v. Sarashi). 'Until today our houses are heated with gas';

3) replacement of the diphthong *yu* by the monophthong *u*: *Suy* (lit. *hyu*) *salkyn, suyk* (lit. *hyuyk*). *Anda su* (lit. *hyu*) *koγonmoγlar* (Aitakova Alsu Faritovna, v. Sarashi). 'The water in it is cold. People don't bathe in it'. *Min ukytushchi* (lit. *ukytusy*) *bulam tip uylamadym, әney min make itte* (Kindyasheva Zimfira Minnimullovna, v. Bruzli). 'I didn't think I would become a teacher, my mum made me';

4) replacing (in very rare cases) the final diphthong *өy* in the verbal affix with *ә*: *Yulybyz gyna da yuk, asphalt tәzәbez* (lit. *tәzәybәz*), *tinelәр* (Ismagilova Fakira Tavafetdinovna, v. Stary Ashap). 'We don't even have a road, they promised to lay asphalt';

5) phonetic transitions in the vowel area:

a) *ә* → *a, a* → *ә* (in the root of words): *Shul ipi kebek ashchytasyu* (lit. *әsetәheң*) (Ismagilova Fakira Tavafetdinovna, v. Stary Ashap). 'Like leavening bread'. *Hәttә* (lit. *hatta*) *min yzem komsomolda eshlәgәshch, utyz ike jәshәtә mine yaңydan komsomolә aldylar* (Kindyasheva Zimfira Minnimullovna, v. Bruzli). 'Even because I worked in the Komsomol they took me back into the Komsomol at the age of thirty-two' (Nazargulova Zemfira Safuanovna, v. 2nd Krasnoyar). *Sәt ashlyrynan bezdә erek bar, anan suң may, kaimәk, cheese, әirән* (lit. *airan*) (Nazargulova Zemfira Safuanovna, v. 2nd Krasnoyar). 'Of dairy products we have cottage cheese, butter, sour cream, cheese, ayran';

b) *ә* → *i* (in the root of words): *Bez keshkenә, bitikey* (lit. *bәlәkәy*) *šәkta, 'class' sikerep uyny iek* (Akbasheva Rashida Shamsemunirovna, Mostovaya v.). 'In childhood we used to play «class», jumping';

c) *u* → *a* (in the root of words, in particular, in indicative pronouns): *Annan* (lit. *unan*) *inde anda* (lit. *unda*) *torgan halyk kitkәnnәр bu yakka zhir ezlәp* (Akbasheva Rashida Shamsemunirovna, Mostovaya v.). 'After that the people who lived there went this way in search of land'. *Alarnyң* (lit. *ularзyң*) *mynda nәsellәre kalzan, ryzhij shchәshchle, bar andyjar* (lit. *undajzar*) (Savaleeva Shagida Gabelvarovna, v. 1 Krasnoyar). 'Their descendants, the red-haired ones, are here to this day';

d) *u* → *o* (in the root of words): *Әle hәzer zә zor* (lit. *zur*) *tygel auylybyz, zor* (lit. *zur*) *bulmasa da, yshel, matur* (Akbasheva Rashida Shamsemunirovna, Mostovaya village). 'And now our village is small, in spite of this it is green, beautiful'. *Yspәe kuryshchaklar, yspәe mebel' keyek shundyj uynshchytar jook* (lit. *yuk*) (Akbasheva Rashida Shamsemunirovna, Mostovaya village). 'There are no toys like beautiful dolls, beautiful furniture'. *Kombaennar soçonan* (lit. *huңnan*) *gyna kilep shchytty, suzyshant soң* (lit. *huң*) *gyna* (Ismagilova Fakira Tavafetdinovna, v. Stary Ashap). 'Combines appeared only later, after the war only'. *Hәzerge toylarny* (lit. *tuizarзy*) *kyzyl toi* (lit. *tui*) *tilәр bit* (Sharipova Nailya Nursayapovna, v. Bruzli). 'Modern weddings are called red weddings';

e) *u* → *y* (in the root of words): *Әgәр kishchәge kәnnә әjтep kyjәan bylsazyz* (lit. *bulhәzәz*), *min alarny ezlәp tә kyjyrejem sezgә* (Kindyasheva Zimfira Minnimullovna, v. Bruzli). 'If you had warned me yesterday, I would have got ready';

6) phonetic transitions in the area of consonants:

a) *s* → *sh* (in the position of the absolute beginning of the word): *Shundyi sh'aklarny* (lit. *sәkterзy*) *haterleim* (Guseva Murshida Galimzyanovna, v. Batyrbai). 'Such moments I remember'. *Tәrlә milli ryzыktar beshәm: kystybyj,*

esh'chposhchmak (lit. *əsposmak*), **esh'chle** (lit. *esle*) *bəlesh bəsherəm* (Nazargulova Zemfira Safuanovna, v. 2nd Krasnoyarsk). 'I cook various national dishes: kystybyy, uchpochmak, belish with stuffing'. **Sh'chynayakty** (lit. *sonayak*) **sh'okor** (lit. *sokor*) *type əytələr* (Nazargulova Zemfira Safuanovna, v. 2nd Krasnoyarsk). 'The cup is called sokor';

b) y → zh' (in the position of the absolute beginning of the word): **Bətən zbirdə** (lit. *[üə]pəə*) *shulyy* (Akbasheva Fanuza Mirzaevna, v. Elpachikha). 'Everywhere like this. Inde *həzergə hətle clubta zhytəksche* (lit. *[ye]təksə*) *bulyp eshleyem* (Nazargulova Zemfira Safuanovna, v. 2nd Krasnoyarsk). 'I still manage the club'. **Min zhidensche** (lit. *[ye]tense*) *bulam byl sem'yada, bezneke zhide* (lit. *[ye]te*) *ee - minke oshch apam, oshch abyym bar ee* (Baltaeva Anisa Kamilovna, v. Chalkovo). 'I am the seventh in the family, there were seven of us, I had three sisters and three brothers';

c) h → s (in the position of the absolute beginning of the word and at the junction of morphemes): **Kiyez itek ultyrtabyz da, ber syharyn** (lit. *chyharyn*), **ikensche syharyn** (lit. *chyharyn*) *keshe yyraklykka ora. Yyrak baryp tōshcə* (lit. *tōshə*) – *prize bula, tōshməcə* (lit. *tōshməhə*) *prize bulmay* (Nazargulova Zemfira Safuanovna, v. 2nd Krasnoyarsk). 'We hold a competition on throwing a boot. If it falls far, the player gets a prize';

d) b → p (in the position of the absolute beginning of the word): **Pilminnar** (lit. *bilməndər*) *yasap ashybyzeye, itt tapsak, itt bulsa. Pirəshkelər pesherep (lit. *besherep*) *ashaybyz bərhəgdən, kyistybyylar pesherep* (lit. *besherep*) *ashybyz* (Abdulova Nagima Khusnullovna, v. Bardabashka). 'When meat is available, we mould dumplings, cook them. Potato pies, kystybiy we cook'. **Palan** (lit. *balan*) *bəleshite without palan* (lit. *balan*) *butka tibež any* (Abdulova Nagima Khusnullovna, v. Bardabashka). 'We call the pie made of calamus a calamus porridge';*

e) b → m (in the position of the absolute beginning of the word): **Myna** (lit. *byna*) *shundyy uyyun uynybyz ie* (Akbasheva Rashida Shamseunirovna, v. Mostovaya). 'This is the kind of game they used to play'.

7) the phenomenon of prostheses and epenthesis: **Oсандыкны** (lit. *chandyk*) *kybese shygaryp attylar* (Aptukova Amina Zakirovna, v. Chalkovo). 'Many people threw away their trunks'. **Bez alty bala bala ber semiyada, byna əle ber seşelem** (lit. *henlem*) *kaldy* (Aitakova Alsu Faritovna, v. Sarashi). 'There are six children in our family, now we have one little sister left'. **Baxsheha totabyz, mal-tyuar asyryybyz** (lit. *açraibyž*), **kortlar asyryybyz** (lit. *açraibyž*) (Yusupova Failya Rashitovna, Verkh-Shlyk village). 'We work in the garden, keep cattle, take care of bees';

8) vowel reduction: **Berse** (lit. *berehe*) *kyzybyz Ufada tora* (Abdulova Nagima Khusnullovna, v. Bardabashka). 'One daughter lives in Ufa';

9) reduction of consonants: **Konechno, auylda v osnovnom irlərneñ kazhdyyunyñ kushamaty bar. Elektən kilgən u** (lit. *ul*) (Nadyrov Rais Zaripovich, v. Verkhny Ashap). 'Of course, in the village every man has a nickname. It has been going on since ancient times'. **Bu taxtalaryn etep torou isheş auryrarak ikə** (lit. *ikən*) **u** (lit. *ul*) *any* (Mustaeva Ramilya Raifovna, v. Sarashi). 'Pushing up these boards, it turns out, is even harder'. **Sezdə yomorka** (lit. *yomortka*) *tilarme?* (Guseva Murshida Galimzyanovna, v. Batyrbaı). 'What do you call your eggs: yomorka?' **Tik utyra** (lit. *ulytra*) *bashlasak, anan soñ ploho*

(Mustaeva Ramilya Raifovna, v. Sarashi). 'If you sit just like that, it's hard to do it'.

The lexeme, occurring in the Haina colloquialism in several variants due to the influence of phonetic phenomena on it, is the postlogue **belən** (Lit. *menən*) 'with'. Firstly, it is the form **belə**, modified due to the loss of the final sound, which was discussed in the previous paragraph. In addition, this postlogue is also used in the form **belə**, formed due to the transition of the sound *ə* into *e*: **Zhirganlar elek uny DT belə** (lit. *menən*), **tractor belə** (lit. *menən*) (Muxsinov Ildar Aukhatovich, v. Iskir). 'They dug it before the DT, with a tractor'. **Koroshche, shular bele** (lit. *menən*) *ber obshchezhitie tordok* (Kindyasheva Zimfira Minnimullovna, v. Bruzli). 'In short, we lived in the same dormitory with them'.

Morphological peculiarities of the Gaina dialect

The following points should be noted as the main features of the Gaina dialect in the field of morphology:

1) affix-free use of the dependent word in isafetas of II type, for example, the forms **ishk aldy** 'courtyard' and **izan ağan açty** 'cellar' used in the literary language are used by Gainin speakers in the forms **ishk al, izən as**. It should be noted that such constructions do not change their form even when case affixes are added to them: *Bezneñ mynda ishk alda* (lit. *ishk aldynda*) *da yçə [pikan], baqıçaada da kyberək. Yul buydagy* (lit. *yul buyyindagy*) *tege neider inde u, borshechek tugelme ikən həzər* (Aptukova Ramilya Abdullovna, v. Batyrbaı). 'It grows here in the yard and more in the garden. It's probably what grows along the edges of the road, if it's not borschtovik'. *Əney əytə torghaneye, zhyen chislala* (lit. *yyyn numeralhynda*) *tudyn, type, zhyen shul june ayda* (lit. *june ayyinda*) *bula bit, sabantuylar* (Urazova Gulsira Magrafovna, v. Suzyan). 'My mum used to say that I was born on the day of a yiyyin (bank holidays), yiyyins are held in June, sabantuys'. *Auyr vakytlar, ashlyk vakytlar* (lit. *aslyk vakytтары*) *bezgə tide inde* (Ismagilova Fakira Tavafetdinovna, v. Stary Ashap). 'Hard, hungry times we had to endure'. *Əney zhanda* (lit. *əney yanynda*) *saugas, yzəm rabochijə kergəs, yzəm isemgə* (lit. *yzemdeñ isemə*) *saumaga kereshtem annary syyr* (Abdulova Nagima Khusnullovna, v. Bardabashka). 'At first I went next to my mother and helped her, then I got a job milking cows myself'. *Kesəl pesherdeç sol ondan* (lit. *holo ononan*) (Abdulova Nagima Khusnullovna, Bardabashka v.). 'Kisel was cooked from oat flour'. *Auył zhiçetkə* (lit. *auyl egetenə*) *kiyeyrə bardym* (Yagafarova Tagzima Baryevna, v. Ishimovo). 'She married a village boy';

2) replacement of the traditionally accepted in Bashkir literary language affixes of the genitive case **-nyñ / -nonı** with the forms **-nyky / -neke** in preposition to the definite word: **Yzemneke** (lit. *yzemdeñ*) *nyndey hənərlərem bar, barysyn da balalarga, ololarga jetkererergə tyryshtym inde* (Kindyasheva Zimfira Minnimullovna, v. Bruzli). 'I tried to teach both adults and children everything I know'. **Bu minke** (lit. *mineneñ*) *tyuyr yskən yzba* (Baltaeva Anisa Kamilovna, Chalkovo v.). 'This is the hut where I was born and grew up'. *Yañy uylda, Kuyan uylyn karshy alganda, min shushy kuyanarnyky* (lit. *kyuyandarzunı*) *doctory buldym inde* (Mustaeva Ramilya Raifovna, v. Sarashi). 'At the New Year, when the year of the Hare met, I was the doctor of these hares'. *Serdash digən gruppə bar, shular bele klubnyky* (lit. *clubtyñ*) *eshen alyp barabyz* (Baltayeva Gulnara Musevna, v. Bardabashka). 'There is a group Serdash («Naperusnitsa»), with its members we conduct the work of the club';

3) widespread use of indefinite verb forms with the affixes -**magha** / -**magā** instead of the literary -**yrga** / -**ergā** by Gainin Bashkirs: *Hāzer inde kul'turnyĭ nejlār ystermāgā* (lit. *yçterergā*) *əjrənep bəttək* (Ramilya Abdullova Aptukova, v. Batyrbai). 'We have learnt to grow cultivated plants now'. *Kazhdıy yaçalyk-niməne yazyp küjyp barmağa* (lit. *baryrga*) *kərək əle* (Aptukova Ramilya Abdullova, v. Batyrbai). 'Every piece of news should be written down'. *Bezzeñ ənejneñ zhyrlamağa* (lit. *yyrlarga*) *vakıty bulmady* (Sharipova Nailya Nursayapovna, v. Bruzli). 'Our mum didn't have time to sing';

4) the specificity of the use of the verb of the long-past definite tense with the auxiliary verb **in** the -**eye/-yi** < -**eye/ -yyyy**, in most cases the indicators of the categories of person and number are attached to the main verb, whereas in the literary language these affixes are attached to the auxiliary verb: *Shokor tuplar uynybizy* (lit. *uinay inek*) (Abdulova Nagima Khusnullovna, v. Bardabashka). 'They used to play «Pit ball». *Bez dā jəsh shchakta sezneñ kebek jerejbezej* (lit. *yərəi inek*). *Kənishne, bez bylyj əjdā ultyrmyjbyzyjy* (lit. *ultyrmay inek*), *bezne ebəraləreje* (lit. *ebəra inelər*) *basularga agitbrigada belən* (Mustaeva Ramilya Raifovna, v. Sarashi). 'We also at a young age walked like that. Of course, we did not sit at home like that, we were sent to the fields with the agitbrigade'. *Tujlar elek əshch kən buladyryjy* (lit. *bula inelər*) (Aptukova Amina Zakirovna, v. Chalkovo). 'We used to celebrate a wedding for three days';

5) the use of the verb of imperative inclination of the second person plural in the form -**уң** / -**ең** (in the affirmative), -**ман** / -**мәң** (in the negative): *Glavnoe keshe arada tauysh shchyzarmañ* (lit. *syəarmazyz*), *əyegezgā kajtkashch ikegez genā razbirat'sya itep alyñ* (lit. *alyəyz*), *no keshe arada ber-beregezgā ypkələgənnə, ashchyulanəzanny kyrsətməskā tyryshyñ* (lit. *tyryshyəyz*) *i, glavnoe, bezgā kajtkanda razborka yasamañ* (lit. *yahamazyz*), *auyzyzyzny zhyryp kiler kerəñ* (lit. *keregez*), *auyzyzyzny zhyryp kajtyr kitəñ* (lit. *kitegez*). *Shulyj tip əjtem inde* (Ilkaeva Indira Gabdəlməlikovna, v. Aklushi). 'The main thing is not to quarrel in front of people, sort things out between yourselves at home, try not to show others your offence against each other and, most importantly, don't make a showdown at our place, come with a smile and leave with a smile. That's what I told mine'. *Bushka zhəroməñ* (lit. *jəroməgez*), *bəkhetegezne teləp zhəroməñ* (lit. *jəroməgez*), *Allahy təəlanən surañ* (lit. *horagy*) (Yagafarova Tagzima Baryevna, v. Ishimovo). 'Do not go in vain, wish yourself happiness, ask Allah'. *Sez miñə berəj nomer birep küjyñ* (lit. *birep küjyəyz*), *irenmej genā fotografiyaga təshərop zhibəremen* (Kindyasheva Zimfira Minnimullovna, v. Bruzli). 'You give me some number, I'll send you a photo';

6) specificity of the use of numerals: a) their combination with the plural form of nouns, which is not peculiar to the literary Bashkir language: *U shchakta bez zhide specialistlar* (lit. *ete specialist*) *eshleebez iek selsovetta, administratsiyada* (Mustaeva Ramilya Raifovna, v. Sarashi). *Ike balam bar, alty onoklarim* (lit. *alty onogom*) *bar* (Kindyasheva Zimfira Minnimullovna, v. Bruzli). 'I have two children, six grandchildren'. *Bez alty balalar* (lit. *alty bala*) *ie ber semiala* (Yagafarova Tagzima Baryevna, v. Ishimovo). 'We had seven children in the family'; b) use of collective numerals in preposition to nouns, which is also inadmissible in the Bashkir literary language: *Əshchəy balalarybyz* (lit. *əs balabyz*) *buldy* (Yusupova Faila Rashitovna, v. Verkh-Shlyk). 'We had three children'. *Anda bar bery khatyn* (lit. *ber katyn*), *u da also auylgaa bagyshlangaan shigarlār-neilār yaza*

kebek (Sharipova Nailya Nursayapovna, v. Bruzli). 'There is a woman there, she also seems to write poems dedicated to her native village'.

7) the use of possessive singular pronouns **minke**, **hineke**, **unyky** in the truncated forms **minke** / **mike**, **sinke**, **uñky**: **Minke** (lit. *minke*) *ətkəy mulla* (Akbasheva Razifa Imamatinovna, v. Konyukovka). 'My father is a mullah'. **Mike** (lit. *mineke*) *profil'* *organizatorskijyrak bara* (Baltayeva Gulnara Musevna, v. Bardabashka). 'My profile is in the form of an organiser'.

8) use of the forms of the dative-adjective case of nominative parts of speech in some cases in an unaffixed form: **Berse** (lit. *berehenə*) – *utyz dərt*, **berse** (lit. *berehenə*) – *egerme dərt*, **berse** (lit. *berehenə*) – *un dərt* (Baltayeva Gulnara Musevna, v. Bardabashka). 'One is thirty-four, the other is twenty-four, the third is fourteen'. **Min** (lit. *mīnə*) *un alty yəsh kenə ie* (Yagafarova Tagzima Baryevna, v. Ishimovo). 'I was only sixteen years old'. *Ənej auyryu buləashch, min* (lit. *miñə*) *kajtyrəa tury kilde dā sigəzəshche klasta bynda ukyp beterep kujdym* (Kindyasheva Zimfira Minnimullovna, v. Bruzli). 'Because of my mother's illness I had to return, I finished eighth grade here';

9) the use of the affixless form of the Locotemporal Case: *Min yzem siksən bish yash* (lit. *hikhən bish yashtə*) *buldym inde* (Akbasheva Razifa Imamatinovna, v. Konyukovka). 'I am already eighty-five years old myself'. *Əteyžən zhide yash* (lit. *ete yashtə*) *kaldym inde min, ətey armyaga kitte* (Abdulova Nagima Khusnullovna, v. Bardabashka). 'I was left without a father at the age of seven, my father was taken to the army'.

10) the use of the forms of the local-temporal case of adjectives formed from the names of seasons with the help of the derivative affixes -**кы** / -**ке** when denoting the time of a phenomenon occurring in one or another season of the year: *Kərtəyk zhyjmağa zhibəraləreje basularəa, kolhozlarəa kəzgədə* (lit. *kəz kəñə, kəzən, kəzgəhən*), *byschkrakta* (Mustaeva Ramilya Raifovna, v. Sarashi). 'In autumn, in the mud, they sent us to collect potatoes in the fields, in the collective farms'. *Klub bezneke agashch ine, kyj, bylyr. Uny kutaryp aldylar kyshkyda* (lit. *kysh kəñə, kyshyn, kyshkyhyn*) (Gulnara Musevna Baltaeva, v. Bardabashka). 'Our club was wooden last year. It was dismantled in winter';

11) active use of the intensifying particle **кы**, which corresponds to the literary **la baha** 'after all' [Mirzhanova, 2006, pp. 259]: *Bezneñ səyləshəy jəmsez, kyj, zhirle halyknyñ, Barda halyknyñ, yzegez beləsez* (Yagafarova Tagzima Baryevna, v. Ishimovo). 'We, the local population, the people of Barda, talk unseemly, you know ourselves'. **“Кы”** *belən kyp syləshəbez bez* (Baltayeva Gulnara Musevna, v. Bardabashka). 'We use the particle **кы** a lot when talking'. *Señlem ana, кыу, ille altynshy yulnyky* (Urazova Gulsira Magrafovna, v. Suzyan). 'My younger sister is fifty-six years old, after all'. *Min kolkhozda eshladem, siñynan, кыу, min yzemneñ kurshedəge abyyny karadym, zhide yyl* (Ilkaeva Sariya Sufiyevna, v. Novy Chad). 'I worked in the collective farm, then I took care of my neighbour for seven years'.

Conclusion

The analysis of the expedition materials in the Bardymsky District of the Perm Territory allowed us to identify certain specific features of the language of the Gainin Bashkirs. Among the peculiarities of the lexicon it is worth mentioning the existence of a large number of dialectisms in the modern environment of the

Gainin Bashkirs. Phonetic peculiarities of the Gainin Bashkir language include such phenomena as the narrowing of the broad vowels а, ə in the position of the stressed closed syllable, phonetic transitions both in the area of vowels and consonants, prosthesis and epenthesis, reduction of vowels and consonants. In terms of morphology, the following are specific for this dialect: the affix-free use of the secondary word in type II isafetes, peculiarities of formation and use of verb forms, nouns, pronouns, as well as the forms of the dative-adjective and local-temporal cases of nominal parts of speech. The comparative analysis of the obtained data in the field of linguistics with the results previously recorded in the scientific literature showed that no special changes in the state of the colloquialism have occurred during half a century.

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